

RTV control in the field in 1984 dry season (DS). Wet seedbeds of highly susceptible TN1 and susceptible IR22 were covered with nylon mesh immediately after sowing to protect seedlings from GLH. Starting 1 d after transplanting (DT), 8 insecticide applications were made at weekly intervals. Disease incidence was recorded at 60 DT.

The same materials and methods were used in a 1985 wet season (WS) trial, but insecticide applications were reduced to five.

In the 1984 DS, RTV infection in plots treated with any of the pyrethroids was significantly lower than in the untreated control. Cypermethrin gave the lowest RTV incidence (see table).

RTV control by 4 synthetic pyrethroids on 2 susceptible rices at IRRI, 1984-85.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation	RTV ^b (% infected hills) at 60 DT			
		1984 DS		1985 WS	
		IR22	TN1	IR22	TN1
Cypermethrin	5 EC	7.8 a	9.6 a	2.5 a	29.6 ab
Ethoproxyfen	20 EC	7.8 a	21.7 abc	2.6 a	22.9 a
Alphamethrin	10 EC	11.5 ab	21.3 abc	3.9 ab	39.4 ab
Deltamethrin	2.5 EC	14.4 ab	29.7 bc	3.3 ab	24.1 a
Control		30.3 c	81.9 d	5.3 b	43.4 b

^aInsecticide was applied at 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, 36, 43, and 50 DT in the 1984 DS and at 1, 20, 34, 49, and 63 DT in the 1985 WS. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

In the 1985 WS, RTV infection was significantly lower on IR22 treated with ethoproxyfen and cypermethrin and on TN1 treated with ethoproxyfen and deltamethrin.

The degree of control with the synthetic pyrethroids improved with more frequent applications early in crop growth. On susceptible varieties, control of RTV by insecticides was low. □

Chemical control of rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzivora*

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A 2-yr study (1982-83) investigated chemical control of GM on irrigated rice in southwestern Burkina Faso, where the pest is prevalent.

Carbofuran at 1.2 kg ai/ha and deltamethrin at 2.5 g ai/ha in a randomized block design with 5 treatments and 5 replications were evaluated. Plot size was 32 rows of 20 hills. Silvershoots at 45, 60, and 75 d after transplanting were counted on 4 rows/plot. Yield was estimated from 20 rows/plot.

Chemical control of rice GM^a. Burkina Faso, 1982-83.

Chemical applied at indicated time					Damage (% silvershoots) 75 DT	Yield (t/ha)
0 DT	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT		
1982						
-	-	-	-	-	26 b	5.39 b
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	-	23 ab	6.31 a
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	18 ab	7.31 a
-	Deltamethrin	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	20 ab	6.40 a
Carbofuran	-	Carbofuran	-	Carbofuran	16 a	6.68 a
1983						
-	-	-	-	-	21 bc	4.91 b
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	16 ab	6.46 a
Carbofuran	-	-	Carbofuran	-	11 a	6.91 a
-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Carbofuran	-	11 a	6.12 a
-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	11 a	5.91 a

^aDT = days after transplanting. In a column and in a year, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Treatments that included at least one application of carbofuran were effective

(see table). Yields were 1-2 t/ha higher than without treatment. □

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Herbicides to control weeds in transplanted rice

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In southeastern Rajasthan, labor for

manual weeding is scarce and expensive. I evaluated herbicides in kharif seasons 1984-85.

Seven herbicides at 2 rates of application were compared with hand weeding 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DT) and an unweeded check. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Weed seed (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) was broadcast at 5 kg/ha immediately after transplanting. Herbicides were applied 6 DT.

Effect of herbicides on weed control in transplanted rice, Kota, India.

Treatment ^a	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield		Panicles/m ²		Panicle wt (g)		Weed dry wt (g/m ²) at harvest		Cost-to-benefit ratio ^b
		(t/ha)								
		1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	
2,4-D EE (G)	0.8	6.7	5.2	312	281	2.8	2.9	170	74	13.2
2,4D EE (G)	1.0	6.9	5.6	321	283	2.7	2.9	167	71	12.5
Oxyfluorfen (G)	0.1	6.1	5.8	311	290	3.2	2.8	190	85	–
Oxyfluorfen (G)	0.15	6.3	5.8	324	295	3.4	2.9	149	82	–
Thiobencarb (G)	1.0	6.7	5.8	320	297	2.9	3.0	188	78	14.5
Thiobencarb (G)	1.5	6.7	5.9	295	284	3.0	2.8	185	70	9.9
Anilofos (EC)	0.3	6.5	4.8	298	295	2.9	2.7	209	95	–
Anilofos (EC)	0.4	6.2	5.3	310	271	2.9	2.8	189	89	–
Butachlor (G)	1.0	6.6	5.4	290	242	3.0	3.0	192	95	12.4
Butachlor (G)	1.5	6.8	5.7	315	253	2.9	2.9	190	96	9.5
Pendimethalin (G)	1.0	7.1	6.1	332	267	3.5	3.3	130	69	18.4
Pendimethalin (G)	1.5	6.9	5.7	310	267	2.8	3.0	163	75	10.7
Butachlor (EN)	1.0	5.7	5.6	299	261	2.5	2.8	210	100	10.8
Butachlor (EN)	1.5	6.1	5.7	300	252	3.3	2.8	180	104	8.5
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DT	–	7.0	6.0	323	262	3.5	3.5	134	15	7.0
Unweeded check	–	4.6	4.0	264	236	2.4	2.3	232	166	–
CD (0.05)		0.2	0.2	3	4	0.1	0.3	2	2	–

^a EE = ethyl ester, G = granules, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, EN = emulsion. Cost of 2,4-D 4G, \$1/kg; thiobencarb 10 G, \$2.15/kg; butachlor 5G, \$1.1/kg; pendimethalin S G, \$1/kg; butachlor 50 EN, \$10/liter; oxyfluorfen and anilofos, not available. ^b Grain, \$160/t; C:B averaged over 2 yr.

Pendimethalin at 1.0 and 1.5 kg ai/ha, thiobencarb at 1.0 and 1.5 kg ai/ha, and 2,4-D at 1.0 kg ai/ha were effective in controlling weeds (see table). These treatments had significantly higher grain yield, more effective tillers, and higher panicle weight than the unweeded check. The highest benefit-to-cost ratio was with pendimethalin at 1 kg ai/ha. □

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Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Yield loss to rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae*

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We conducted two experiments with potted plants to determine yield loss to *H. oryzae*.

IR20 seedlings raised in sterile soil were transplanted 21 d after sowing at 4 seedlings/pot. Treatments were rice root nematodes inoculated at 1 and at 10/g soil and an untreated check, in 8

Effect of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* on height and yield of rice. ^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85.

Treatment (nematodes/g soil)	Plant ht (cm)			Grain		Straw	
	30 DT	60 DT	At harvest	Yield (g/4 hills)	Reduction (%)	Yield (g/4 hills)	Reduction (%)
0	38 a	62 a	79 a	44.1 a	–	34.1 a	–
1	34 b	58 b	70 b	32.2 b	26.9	26.0 b	22.9
10	30 c	54 c	68 c	26.6 c	39.7	19.7 c	42.2
CD (0.05)		1		5.2	–	3.5	–

^a Mean for 2 pot experiments, with 8 replications each. DT = days after transplanting. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

replications.

Yield losses were 27% with 1 nematode/g soil and 40% with 10

nematodes/g soil (see table). Straw yields were 23% less with 1 nematode and 42% less with 10 nematodes. □

Control of rice root nematode with carbofuran

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The effect of carbofuran on populations of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella*

mucronata and on growth characteristics of rice were measured in microplot field experiments in 1983 and 1984 rainy seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 4 treatments and 5 replications in 16-m² subplots.

Treatments were seedlings from an untreated nursery (T1), seedlings from a

carbofuran-treated nursery (T2), seedlings from the untreated nursery with carbofuran applied 50 d after transplanting (DT) (T3), and seedlings from the carbofuran-treated nursery with carbofuran at 50 DT (T4). All applications were at 1 kg ai/ha.

Experimental field soil was loamy clay with pH 6.4. Recommended NPK